

SciDis Database

The **SciDis (Scientific Dissemination) Database** is a collection of digital texts responding to a global urge to **transfer scientific knowledge to the wide public and transform science communication into a public good**. To meet that end, dissemination practices are rapidly proliferating and evolving in the digital medium, as complex discursive phenomena that require recontextualization processes to make disciplinary expert knowledge accessible to multiple, diversified audiences.

To find out more about the compilation and future analyses of the SciDis Database, you can read about the [aims and research questions](#) and [methodological procedures](#) of our current research project.

Our SciDis Database aims to **depict digital scientific practices related to the creation and circulation of knowledge and findings concerning some of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**. In this project, we analyse digital discursive practices which revolve around Goal no. 3, connected with good health and well-being, Goal no. 7, referring to affordable and clean energy, Goal no. 12, hinging upon responsible consumption and production, and Goal no. 13, focusing on climate action. Similarly, from the perspective of our project, these four SDGs (no. 3, 7, 12 and 13) are all encompassed in Goal no. 17, for they contribute to the revitalization of the global partnership for sustainable development.

Thus, as seen in the graphic below, we have selected **three main disciplines (health, economy and natural sciences)** with two fine-grained subtopics, each tightly linked to the SDGs presented above. They have been chosen due to their high social relevance, which precisely drives

the interest to produce and disseminate specialized knowledge for the wide public. The possible knowledge asymmetries among expert and non-expert audiences steer the recontextualization processes in a multiplicity of modes, media and contexts that are maximized in the digital medium.

Scientific disciplines and sub-topics		Specific SDGs
HEALTH		
Physical activity and nutrition Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages		
ECONOMY		
Sustainability Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns		
NATURAL SCIENCES		
Energy efficiency Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts		

In our SciDis project, the notion of recontextualization is conceived as a multidimensional process which goes beyond linguistic reformulation, and entails social, cognitive, pragmatic and discursive dimensions, too. In the context of science dissemination, recontextualizing scientific knowledge entails extracting it from its original expert source and reshaping it so that it fits in other (non-)expert environments. The resultant shape is to some extent determined by the digital affordances available in the platform where dissemination practices take place.

As a result, the SciDis Database –visually summarized in the graphic below– aims to cover a wide diversity of digital professional practices found in the context of science dissemination and characterized by the reliance on recontextualization.

In addition to the discipline and topic there are two different variables that we have carefully considered in order to select and classify the digital discursive practices that we intend to analyse. The **first variable** concerns **the typology of the practices** that we have chosen and points at the dichotomy between i) texts hosted within websites as specific digital spaces where knowledge is explained and ii) social networking sites as platforms with unique affordances for social interaction.

Web-hosted practices

Dissemination practices that are hosted in websites and subsequent webpages, generated and consumed as layers of recontextualized scientific information (featuring domain-specific specialized knowledge) through which users can navigate.

Social media practices

Dissemination practices which take place in platforms characterised by their interactivity potential whose driving force is the promotion of user interaction – in this case, interaction around scientific knowledge.

The **second variable** touches upon the **generator of the content** that is published in the digital discursive practices under scrutiny in our SciDis Database. A first scenario involves practices in which **the individuals holding scientific knowledge** create and distribute the information and data. The source of knowledge and the individual disseminating it thus coincide. We have coined these as “author-generated practices”. A second scenario is represented by practices in which the **author of the text is different from the source of knowledge** and/or the individuals generating it. We refer to this phenomenon as “writer-mediated practices”.

Author-generated knowledge

It concerns practices endorsed by users themselves, irrespective of their individual profiles (e.g. scientists, scholars, lay citizens) and for a variety of dissemination purposes.

It involves practices in which the role of a mediator (e.g. journalists, editors, scriptwriters) comes into play between the author and the scientific knowledge to be disseminated.

Writer-mediated knowledge